

Comparative Analysis of Retrieval Methods for RAG over Electronic Design Automation Documentation

Gursimran S. Sodhi
OnDevTra Technologies
Bangalore, India
gursimran.sodhi@ondevtra.com

Abstract—Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) has emerged as a key paradigm for grounding large language models in domain-specific knowledge. However, the relative effectiveness of different retrieval strategies for highly technical Electronic Design Automation (EDA) documentation remains understudied. We present a systematic comparative evaluation of four retrieval methods—Simple Vector Search, MultiVector Retrieval, RAPTOR (Recursive Abstractive Processing for Tree-Organized Retrieval), and ColBERT (Contextualized Late Interaction over BERT)—across three EDA documentation corpora of varying complexity: online API documentation (324 chunks), a static timing analysis textbook (292 chunks), and a dense EDA tool command reference manual (648 chunks). Using an LLM-as-Judge evaluation framework with GPT-4o-mini scoring retrieved chunks on a 0–3 relevance scale across four query categories, we find that no single method dominates all scenarios. MultiVector Retrieval excels on structured online documentation (+40% over baseline), while RAPTOR and ColBERT achieve the highest relevance (2.0/3.0) on complex textbook content. For dense command references, both MultiVector and RAPTOR tie (1.6/3.0) while ColBERT’s token-level matching shows diminished returns. We provide cost-performance analysis showing ColBERT achieves competitive quality at zero API cost, and discuss implications for production EDA RAG system design. All benchmark code and the open-source dataset are publicly available.

Index Terms—Retrieval-Augmented Generation, RAG, Electronic Design Automation, Vector Search, ColBERT, RAPTOR, MultiVector Retrieval, LLM Evaluation

I. INTRODUCTION

Large Language Models (LLMs) have demonstrated remarkable capabilities across diverse tasks, yet they remain prone to hallucination when queried about domain-specific technical content [1]. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) addresses this by grounding model responses in retrieved evidence from a knowledge base. While RAG has been widely adopted in general-purpose applications, its deployment in Electronic Design Automation (EDA) workflows presents unique challenges.

EDA documentation is characterized by: (1) dense technical terminology mixing natural language with command syntax, equations, and signal names; (2) hierarchical conceptual structures where understanding requires cross-referencing multiple sections; and (3) a mixture of precise factual content (command syntax, parameter values) and conceptual explanations

(design methodologies, tradeoff analyses). These characteristics stress retrieval systems differently than typical document corpora.

Several advanced retrieval strategies have been proposed to address limitations of simple vector similarity search. Multi-Vector Retrieval [2] generates LLM summaries of document chunks and retrieves based on summary embeddings, returning the original full-context chunks. RAPTOR [3] constructs a hierarchical tree of summaries through recursive clustering and abstractive summarization, enabling retrieval at multiple levels of abstraction. ColBERT [4] employs token-level late interaction, computing fine-grained similarity through MaxSim operations between query and document token embeddings.

Despite the proliferation of these methods, systematic comparisons on technical EDA documentation are scarce. Prior RAG benchmarks focus on general knowledge [5], legal [6], or biomedical domains [7], leaving a gap in understanding which retrieval strategies best serve EDA engineers querying tool documentation, design textbooks, and command references.

Contributions. This paper presents:

- A systematic benchmark comparing four retrieval methods across three EDA documentation corpora of varying complexity and structure.
- An LLM-as-Judge evaluation framework with four query categories (specific fact, conceptual, cross-chapter, broad overview) designed for technical documentation assessment.
- Cost-performance analysis revealing that locally-executed ColBERT achieves competitive relevance at zero API cost.
- Actionable guidelines for selecting retrieval methods based on document characteristics in production EDA RAG systems.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Retrieval-Augmented Generation

RAG was introduced by Lewis et al. [1] as a method to combine parametric and non-parametric memory for knowledge-intensive tasks. The standard pipeline involves: document chunking, embedding via dense retrieval models, storage in a vector database, and similarity-based retrieval at query time.

LangChain [2] and LlamaIndex [8] have popularized this pattern, with extensions including hybrid search combining dense and sparse retrieval [9].

B. Advanced Retrieval Strategies

MultiVector Retrieval decouples the representation used for retrieval from the content returned to the LLM. By generating summaries, hypothetical questions, or other transformations of document chunks, the retrieval step operates over a semantically enriched space while the generation step receives full original context [2].

RAPTOR [3] addresses the limitation that flat vector stores cannot capture hierarchical document structure. By recursively clustering chunks, generating abstractive summaries at each level, and indexing all levels together, RAPTOR enables retrieval at the appropriate level of abstraction for a given query.

ColBERT [4] introduces late interaction, where query and document tokens are independently encoded, then compared via MaxSim—for each query token, the maximum similarity to any document token is computed and summed. This preserves token-level matching signals lost in single-vector representations, particularly beneficial for queries containing precise technical terms.

C. RAG Evaluation

RAGAS [5] provides metrics for RAG quality including faithfulness and answer relevance. LLM-as-Judge evaluation [10] uses language models to assess quality, offering scalability over human annotation while maintaining reasonable correlation with human judgments. We adopt this approach with domain-specific rubrics.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Datasets

We evaluate on three EDA documentation corpora selected to represent the spectrum of document types encountered in practice:

- 1) **OpenROAD Documentation** (Dataset A): 15 pages of online API documentation from the OpenROAD open-source EDA toolchain [11], licensed under BSD-3. Characteristics: concise command descriptions, structured format, moderate technical density. Split into 324 chunks.
- 2) **Static Timing Analysis Textbook** (Dataset B): 158 pages (Chapters 3–7) from a graduate-level STA textbook covering delay models, timing arcs, constraints, and path analysis. Characteristics: dense mathematical content, conceptual depth, extensive cross-referencing between chapters. Split into 292 chunks.
- 3) **EDA Tool Command Reference** (Dataset C): 352 pages from an industry FPGA synthesis tool command reference manual covering Tcl commands, GUI operations, and synthesis workflows. Characteristics: highly structured command syntax, repetitive formatting, large volume. Split into 648 chunks.

All documents were chunked using `RecursiveCharacterTextSplitter` with chunk size 1000 and overlap 200, using separators `["\n\n", "\n", ". ", " ", ""]`.

B. Retrieval Methods

1) *Simple Vector Search (Baseline)*: Documents are embedded using OpenAI `text-embedding-3-small` (1536 dimensions) and stored in PGVector [12]. Retrieval uses cosine similarity with $k=4$.

2) *MultiVector Retrieval*: Each chunk is summarized by GPT-4o-mini into a 2–3 sentence technical summary. Summaries are embedded and stored in PGVector; original chunks are maintained in an in-memory document store. Retrieval matches against summary embeddings but returns full original chunks.

3) *RAPTOR*: Chunk embeddings are clustered using K-means ($n_1 = \lceil N/12 \rceil$ clusters). Each cluster is summarized by GPT-4o-mini. Level-1 summaries are re-clustered ($n_2 = \lceil n_1/4 \rceil$) and summarized again to produce Level-2 nodes. All documents (original chunks + Level-1 + Level-2 summaries) are embedded and indexed together in PGVector.

4) *ColBERT (Token-Level MaxSim)*: We use the `colbert-ir/colbertv2.0` model via `sentence-transformers` to compute token-level embeddings. For each query, we compute MaxSim scores:

$$S(q, d) = \sum_{i=1}^{|q|} \max_{j=1}^{|d|} \mathbf{q}_i^T \mathbf{d}_j \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{q}_i and \mathbf{d}_j are token embeddings for query token i and document token j respectively. The top- k documents by $S(q, d)$ are retrieved.

C. Evaluation Framework

1) *Query Design*: For each dataset, we design 10 queries spanning four categories:

- **Specific Fact** (3 queries): Precise factual lookups (e.g., command syntax, equation forms).
- **Conceptual** (3 queries): Understanding of principles and relationships.
- **Cross-Chapter** (2 queries): Information spanning multiple document sections.
- **Broad Overview** (2 queries): High-level summaries requiring synthesis.

2) *LLM-as-Judge Scoring*: Each retrieved chunk (top-4 per query) is scored by GPT-4o-mini on a 0–3 scale:

- **3**: Directly answers the query
- **2**: Contains related, useful information
- **1**: Marginally relevant
- **0**: Not relevant

We report: (1) average relevance score across all queries and chunks, (2) normalized score (relevance / 3 × 100%), and (3) NDCG@4 for ranking quality.

3) *Cost Estimation*: API costs are estimated using published pricing: `text-embedding-3-small` at \$0.020/M tokens, GPT-4o-mini input at \$0.150/M tokens, output at \$0.600/M tokens. ColBERT runs locally with zero API cost.

IV. RESULTS

A. Overall Performance

Table I presents aggregate results across all three datasets.

Key findings from the overall comparison:

No single method dominates. The best-performing method varies by dataset: MultiVector leads on Dataset A (+40% over baseline), while RAPTOR and ColBERT tie on Dataset B, and MultiVector/RAPTOR tie on Dataset C.

Document complexity matters. On the simplest dataset (A: online docs), the gap between methods is largest (1.08 to 1.50). On the most complex dataset (B: textbook), all methods perform relatively well (1.88 to 2.00), suggesting that rich content provides sufficient signal for all retrieval strategies.

ColBERT offers a cost-free competitive alternative. ColBERT matches or approaches the best method on Datasets A and B at zero API cost, though it falls behind on the dense command reference (Dataset C).

Fig. 1 visualizes the relevance comparison across all three datasets, clearly showing MultiVector’s dominance on Dataset A and the convergence of methods on Dataset B.

Fig. 1: Average retrieval relevance (0–3) for each method across the three EDA datasets. MultiVector leads on structured docs (A), while methods converge on complex textbook content (B).

B. Performance by Query Type

Table II breaks down results by query category, averaged across datasets.

MultiVector excels at specific facts. The summary-based retrieval in MultiVector captures key technical terms and relationships, improving specific fact retrieval by 33% over baseline.

RAPTOR benefits cross-chapter queries. The hierarchical structure of RAPTOR summaries naturally bridges concepts

spanning multiple sections, achieving the highest cross-chapter score (1.42).

Conceptual queries show smallest gaps. All advanced methods achieve similar performance (1.61–1.81) on conceptual queries, suggesting that semantic understanding is well-served by embedding-based approaches regardless of architecture.

ColBERT underperforms on broad overview. Token-level MaxSim matching favors precise term overlap, which disadvantages broad queries requiring synthesis across topics.

Fig. 2 illustrates these differences, showing MultiVector’s advantage on specific facts and RAPTOR’s strength on cross-chapter queries.

Fig. 2: Performance breakdown by query type, averaged across all three datasets. MultiVector excels at specific fact retrieval; RAPTOR leads on cross-chapter queries.

C. Cost-Performance Tradeoff

Table III reveals the cost-performance tradeoff on the largest dataset. MultiVector achieves the highest relevance but at 15× the cost of RAPTOR with identical relevance scores. ColBERT provides a completely free alternative that still outperforms RAPTOR on Dataset B. For production deployment, the choice depends on whether API costs or quality is the primary constraint. Fig. 3 plots this tradeoff on a log-scale cost axis, highlighting ColBERT’s position at zero cost.

D. Indexing Scalability

Indexing time scales differently across methods (Fig. 4). Simple Vector and ColBERT scale linearly with corpus size (4s and 15–21s respectively). MultiVector scales linearly with API latency (~170–305s), while RAPTOR exhibits super-linear growth due to recursive clustering (225–632s), making it the least practical for large corpora.

V. DISCUSSION

A. When to Use Each Method

Based on our results, we offer the following practical guidelines for EDA RAG system designers:

TABLE I: Overall Performance Across Three EDA Datasets

Dataset	Method	Rel.	Score %	NDCG @4	Query (ms)	Index (s)	Chunks	Cost (\$)
A: OpenROAD (15 pg, 324 ch)	Simple Vector	1.08	35.8	0.773	410	4.4	324	0.0013
	MultiVector	1.50	50.0	0.919	400	169.6	324	0.0230
	RAPTOR	1.18	39.2	0.791	400	298.6	357	0.0075
	ColBERT	1.10	36.7	0.862	500	15.9	324	free
B: STA Textbook (158 pg, 292 ch)	Simple Vector	1.95	65.0	0.979	517	4.0	292	0.0015
	MultiVector	1.88	62.5	0.959	344	172.6	292	0.0230
	RAPTOR	2.00	66.7	0.945	433	224.1	322	0.0075
	ColBERT	2.00	66.7	0.959	205	13.7	292	free
C: EDA Cmd Ref (352 pg, 648 ch)	Simple Vector	1.53	50.8	0.936	397	4.0	648	0.0032
	MultiVector	1.60	53.3	0.909	417	304.7	648	0.0504
	RAPTOR	1.60	53.3	0.945	371	632.4	715	0.0166
	ColBERT	1.35	45.0	0.909	169	20.8	648	free

TABLE II: Average Relevance by Query Type (All Datasets)

Query Type	Simple	Multi	RAPT.	ColB.
Specific Fact	1.36	1.81	1.61	1.56
Conceptual	1.78	1.81	1.81	1.61
Cross-Chapter	1.33	1.29	1.42	1.38
Broad Overview	1.54	1.50	1.42	1.29

TABLE III: Cost-Performance Summary (Dataset C, Largest Corpus)

Method	Rel.	Index (s)	API Calls	Cost (\$)
Simple Vector	1.53	4.0	0	0.0032
ColBERT	1.35	20.8	0	0.0000
RAPTOR	1.60	632.4	67	0.0166
MultiVector	1.60	304.7	648	0.0504

Simple Vector Search remains a strong baseline, particularly for complex textbook-style content where it achieves 1.95/3.0 relevance with sub-second indexing and minimal cost. It should be the default starting point.

MultiVector Retrieval is recommended when the corpus consists of structured, repetitive documentation (API references, command manuals) where LLM-generated summaries can capture the essence of each section more effectively than raw text embeddings. The +40% improvement on online documentation justifies the indexing cost.

RAPTOR is best suited for long-form technical documents requiring synthesis across sections. Its hierarchical summarization naturally bridges concepts, evidenced by its leading cross-chapter performance. However, indexing costs make it impractical for frequently-updated corpora.

ColBERT is ideal for cost-constrained deployments and scenarios requiring fast query times. Its token-level matching preserves signal for technical terms (command names, signal identifiers) but loses effectiveness on broad conceptual queries. The zero API cost makes it attractive for offline or air-gapped EDA environments.

Cost vs. Quality (Dataset C: 648 chunks)

Fig. 3: Cost vs. quality tradeoff on Dataset C (648 chunks). ColBERT achieves competitive relevance at zero API cost. RAPTOR matches MultiVector quality at 3× lower cost.

B. Implications for EDA RAG Systems

Our results suggest that production EDA RAG systems should employ *adaptive retrieval*—routing queries to different retrieval backends based on query type. A lightweight classifier could direct specific-fact queries to MultiVector, cross-section queries to RAPTOR, and use ColBERT as a fast fallback. This hybrid approach would combine the strengths observed across our experiments.

The strong performance of Simple Vector on the STA textbook (1.95/3.0) also challenges the assumption that advanced retrieval is always necessary. For well-written, semantically rich documents, simple embedding similarity captures relevant passages effectively. Fig. 5 provides a multi-dimensional view of method performance on Dataset B, showing each method’s strengths and weaknesses across query types and ranking quality.

C. Limitations

Our study has several limitations: (1) the LLM-as-Judge evaluation, while scalable, may not perfectly correlate with

Fig. 4: Indexing time vs. corpus size for each retrieval method.

Fig. 5: Radar chart showing multi-dimensional performance on Dataset B (STA Textbook). Each axis represents a query type or NDCG@4 (scaled to 0–3). ColBERT and RAPTOR show complementary strengths.

human expert judgments for highly technical EDA content; (2) we use a fixed chunking strategy across all datasets—adaptive chunking based on document structure could improve results; (3) our ColBERT implementation uses brute-force MaxSim rather than optimized approximate nearest-neighbor search, affecting query latency at scale; (4) we evaluate retrieval quality in isolation, not end-to-end generation quality.

D. Future Work

We plan to extend this benchmark with: (1) additional open-source EDA datasets including SKY130 PDK documentation; (2) hybrid retrieval combining BM25 sparse search with dense retrieval via Reciprocal Rank Fusion; (3) end-to-end

RAG evaluation measuring answer quality, not just retrieval relevance; (4) human expert evaluation on a subset of queries to calibrate LLM-as-Judge accuracy.

VI. CONCLUSION

We presented a systematic comparison of four retrieval methods for RAG over EDA documentation, finding that retrieval strategy effectiveness depends on document characteristics. MultiVector Retrieval provides the best quality for structured online documentation, RAPTOR and ColBERT tie for complex textbook content, and RAPTOR matches MultiVector for dense command references. ColBERT emerges as a compelling cost-free alternative achieving competitive relevance without API dependencies. These findings inform the design of production EDA RAG systems, suggesting that adaptive retrieval strategies routing queries to method-specific backends offer the most robust approach. Our benchmark code and open-source dataset are available at: <https://github.com/guris12/eda-rag-benchmark>.

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